

Guide to Digital Music Editing

Project directed by Philippe VENDRIX (CNRS) and Augustin BRAUD (CNRS)

translated by Zoe Saunders

in collaboration with :

- Ailin Arjmand (University of Tours)
- Christelle Chaillou (CNRS)
- Kévin Roger (University of Lorraine)
- Suzy Piat (University of Tours)
- Vincent Besson (CNRS)

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1.1 What is Included in this Guide ? What is it not ? Who is its Intended Audience ?

Digital editions of music occupy an increasingly prominent place in the international musicological landscape. While it is impossible, due to the lack of exhaustive catalogues,¹ to enumerate them, their presence is becoming more significant. Large-scale national and European projects dedicate substantial portions of their programs to the production of digital editions. This enthusiasm, though still far from comparable to the digitization of recorded music or musical sources, raises questions for both their creators and users.² This guide aims to address some of those questions. Developed from reflections initiated in 2023 within the Consortium-HN MUSICA2 of the research infrastructure HumaNum,³ it is intended to be regularly updated to incorporate innovations that affect the world of music and digital technology, and aims to propose a framework to counter obsolescence by recommending workflows that ensure the longterm sustainability of data and the infrastructures that host it.

The guide aims to accompany the essential stages of a digital music edition, from its conception to its dissemination. It therefore includes information, recom-

mendations, suggestions, and guidance addressing both the definition of the corpus to be edited and the choices involved in web-based visualization. It attempts to account for the evolving context in which musicology operates, both in terms of its ties to musical practice and its positioning within the cultural production chain. In a context in which an increasing number of projects require a strong digital foundation in line with Open Access⁴ policies and the expectations of research funding bodies, the following pages are intended as a resource for identifying the scientific actions necessary to meet current challenges and to emphasize the critical role of the underlying logistics that support the technical and scholarly aspects of such projects. Although musicology is not itself a Cultural and Creative Industry (CCI), it is closely related to one of that sector's most dynamic and diverse fields, audio recording and distribution. In other words, while this guide primarily concerns heritage science, it also addresses the role that musicology as a scientific discipline seeks to play within the rapidly expanding realm of CCIs.⁵

- 1 The contribution of the *Directory of Digital Scholarship in Music*, compiled by the Digital Humanities Interest Group (DHIG) between 2018 and 2023, should be mentioned : <https://rutgersdh.github.io/musicdh/reuse/>
- 2 Two research seminars were organized in Tours, from July 3-5, 2023, and February 11-12, 2025. Participants included Nicolas Bucher, Laurent Guillo, Theodora Psychoyou, Thomas Lecomte, Saraswathi Shukla, Christelle Chaillou, Christelle Cazaux, David Chappuis, Rémi Bonnin, Richard Freedman, Léontine Fortin, Carlo Bossi, Marco Gurrieri, Kévin Roger, Laurent Pugin, Ugo Bindini, Aurélien Balland-Chatignon, Philippe Vendrix, Augustin Braud, Ailin Arjmand, and Vincent Besson.
- 3 See <https://www.huma-num.fr/quest-ce-que-l-ir-huma-num> for more information on this research infrastructure.
- 4 A mode of disseminating research which results in a free digital format, in compliance with copyright law.
- 5 For more information on the Cultural and Creative Industries, see the program pepr-icare : <https://pepr-icare.fr/about-icare/project/?lang=en>.

Heritage sciences, production chain. These terms alone convey the scope of the field covered in this guide. It is therefore necessary to consider certain notions and concepts before beginning any editorial project. Nothing in this domain is unequivocal : the fact that a musical work is considered part of our heritage does not mean that it is free from legal constraints ! A production chain may choose not to use subscription-based tools. The act of editing, digital or not, takes place within a social, economic, legal, and cultural context that invariably requires preliminary reflection. Under European law, the status of a scholarly editor is distinct from that of a creator, but it is precisely this distance that must be assessed with care before undertaking an editorial project, as it can easily give rise to difficult and potentially damaging conflicts for the scholarly project.¹

At the conclusion of the project, the question of obsolescence will inevitably arise. Like legal considerations, it lies beyond the scope of this guide, yet it remains a fundamental, albeit intangible, element upon which the entire project must be constructed.²

Any editorial project requires both human and financial resources. It remains difficult even today to quantify in hours or material costs the production of a digital musical edition.³ An estimate based on the *Gesualdo Online* project values a single page of music (in A4 format) at approximately 250 euros, which the entire process from the acquisition of source materials to the online publication of files in a functional and userfriendly format.⁴ Undertaking a digital edition therefore

requires mobilizing resources and, if necessary, obtaining funding from sponsors. This guide will not provide a fixed “grid” of such costs, which would inevitably vary depending on the type of corpus, from a plainchant antiphon to a 21st century opera, from a popular song of the second half of the 20th century to a 17th century collection of organ tablatures. Assessing the corpus is a crucial step that involves considering the feasibility of the project, whether it requires the participation of numerous specialists or to can be completed by a single researcher familiar with the repertoire in question. From these considerations, a financial appraisal of the editorial project can be drawn, which would be included in any funding application, whether the project is purely editorial or part of a broader scientific project.

1.1.1. A Resource for Design and Implementation

Although conceived as a resource to support the design of digital editions, this guide does not claim to address the technical issues that inevitably arise and recur with each editorial project. It is not limited to meeting the requirements of paleographic work and or collating sources ; it also anticipates the ways in which the text to be transmitted will be used through its reading formats, the role of paratext and metadata, and the management of notation systems employed in both early and contemporary music.

Accordingly, this guide will not address specific cases, but rather outline the full range of issues that should be considered when undertaking a digital

1 On the question of music publishing rights, see Allen Bargfrede and Cecily Mak, *Music Law in the Digital Age*, Boston, Berklee University Press, 2009.

2 On obsolescence, see Rosenthal, D.S.H., “Format Obsolescence: Assessing the Threat and the Defenses”, *Library Hi Tech*, 28/2 (2020), p. 195-210.

3 For a European approach to the subject, see European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Kramer, B., *Study on scientific publishing in Europe – Development, diversity, and transparency of costs*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2024, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/89349>.

4 Ph. Vendrix, *Gesualdo online, the economic model of a digital music edition*, 2024, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13959918>.

music edition. It is therefore structured around three main themes: (1) **the nature** of a digital edition; (2) **the tools** and processes required for its production; and (3) **recommendations** for an efficient design that meets the FAIR¹ principles that govern any digital humanities initiative.

Addressing these three themes raises a series of questions of varying level of detail, but whose implications are significant for the nature of the results obtained through what is often a lengthy process. This guide provides responses to both general and specific questions, including:

- How is music encoded?
- Are there legal constraints that apply to a digital edition?
- How can critical thinking be applied to a digital edition?
- How can the digital twin represented by the new edition be linked to its source and its notation?
- What connections should be established between a digital edition and other available digital resources (RISM, Gallica, etc.)?
- How can the planned editorial work be aligned with European cultural policies?
- On what grounds can musicology be considered a data science?
- What relationships can a digital edition forge with the CCIs, and with music platforms in particular?
- Does a community of music editors exist?

In order to respect best practices, it is necessary to establish recommendations for monitoring the quality of both data and encoding. This guide therefore encourages

researchers to exercise critical judgement and to assume full editorial responsibility in order to ensure that Open Access policies are upheld through scientific expertise. One of the fundamental principles of digital editing is to preserve the integrity of the content while providing it a renewed perspective.

From a philological standpoint, digital editions raise a number of questions, especially concerning critical editions. When preparing a digital critical edition, it is essential to consider the computational readability of the data, and therefore its encoding, as well as usability for performers. Since these two dimensions often pull digital editorial work in different directions, they should be approached in a complementary manner to enhance intelligibility, clarify objectives, and anticipate the contexts in which the edition will ultimately be used, whether for research, performance, etc.

Because digital editing is far more complex than simply reproducing musical examples or excerpts intended for distribution as downloadable .pdf files, particular attention must be paid to achieving a high level of interactivity through features specifically adapted to encoded musical text. Thus in the course of developing a digital edition, scholars must ensure compliance with the FAIR principles, while also assessing the technical feasibility of publishing the data online and maintaining its accessibility over time.

1.1.2. Quality Principles and the Need for Best Practices

The guide is intended for musicologists and musicians working in teaching and research institutions as well as for any knowledgeable individual, professional or

¹ The FAIR principles are a group of recommendations that aim to improve accessibility, interoperability, and reuse of digital resources. The original publication of these principles was drawn up in 2016 in the journal *Scientific Data*, see M. Wilkinson, M. Dumontier, I. Aalbersbert *et al.* "The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship.", *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>.

amateur, wishing to venture into digital editing. In Europe, the former are generally encouraged to disseminate their work in accordance with Open Access principles, whereas the latter typically operate independently and can be broadly divided into two categories : the first makes their editions freely accessible through dedicated websites, while the second produces digital editions for strictly limited use (within a performing ensemble, for example). Evaluations of Open Access projects often focus on what can be described as the quality process.

- How is the peer review, which is essential to any scientific process, conducted?
- How can one balance making the resource fully accessible and preserving the expertise involved?

Attempting to answer these questions requires situating the digital edition within the musical philological tradition of the second half of the 19th century. It is also important to examine the relationship between a digital edition and what is conventionally referred to as a critical edition, since the critical edition is by no means the only point of reference for those who produce digital editions. Establishing connections with editorial traditions is especially pertinent because, as this guide illustrates, the three pillars on which a digital edition rests—tools, content, and presentation¹—are conceptually closely aligned to what the founders in the 19th century conceived. This conceptual proximity calls for careful nuance :

- How does downloadable .pdf file differ from a printed edition?
- How can it be characterized digitally?
- Are there multiple levels of digitalization for a musical edition?

It thus appears necessary to provide a guide to clarify what “digital” truly means:

- Are “digital” editions intended to be understood by computers or by performers?
- What is the defining feature of a digital edition in terms of intelligibility?

We wish to emphasize a particular point of caution regarding the rendering of encoded files. While the prospect of an aesthetically pleasing visualization is certainly appealing, it may result in encoding that is less readable and less logical for machines, thereby limiting the file’s interoperability and the potential for performing analytical tasks that make full use of the digital edition. One best practice would therefore be to encourage users to prioritize the use of established standards in order to ensure maximum readability and interoperability of files.

1.2. Design conditions

If we consider only the field of digital editing produced within the framework of institutional research (carried out by members of recognized teaching and research institutions as defined by European criteria), it is essential to address the conditions under which editorial projects are conceived, often in response to specific requirements set out in calls for proposals.

Beyond these particular cases, shaped by the nature of the academic or research institution, as well as by local conditions of scientific production and dissemination, it is equally important to situate the dynamics of digital music editing within a broader perspective that connects European research with the wider field of music scholarship.

1.2.1. On Scientific, Political, and Editorial Context

Scientific knowledge today is built largely upon digital resources ; this is as true for disciplines such as economics or archaeology as it is for musicology. Some of the most emblematic projects initiated by the musicological community in the mid20th

1 See M. Caraci Vela, *Musical philology. Institutions, history and critical approaches*, Pisa, Edizioni ETS, 2015.

century—namely RISM and RILM—have long since undergone their digital transformation. It would now seem unusual to conduct original research without relying on online resources in one way or another, just as disseminating research through journals or publishers can no longer dispense with digital tools. Visibility of research results is the primary and perhaps most compelling reason for this shift, though not the only one. A recent study conducted by *COST EarlyMuse* on the state of monumental editions in Europe has in fact identified numerous arguments in favor of digital editions, even when they concern “historical” projects.¹

Beyond the large-scale “monumental” projects, some of which have been ongoing since the 19th century, the question of the economic context has at times become particularly pressing. Rising paper costs, reduced library acquisitions, distribution expenses, and shifting market trends all combine to make the work of a publisher extremely challenging and risky when it comes to producing music volumes. The distribution of forces and dynamics in the publishing sector are similar to those of the music recording industry. Production and distribution channels increasingly converge under the control of a few major players capable of sustaining full production costs. Yet even these powerful enterprises cannot disregard the contribution of scholars, and thus the value of their research, which is generally supported by public institutions. It would be utopian to imagine complete independence among the various parties involved : the scholar who prepares the

edition, the policymaker who facilitates it through institutional support, and the publisher who ensures its production and dissemination. To this trio must now be added a fourth and essential actor: technology.

The context with all its complexity invites a rethinking of methods, objectives, as well as of content and its modes of presentation. Such reflection, however, should not be limited to those producing digital critical editions ; it must also include users, encouraging them to create a new relationship between musicology and performance. In other words, it is equally necessary to consider the visibility of musicology as a scientific discipline and its impact on the world of musical performance.² In this respect, it is worth noting the significant scale of editorial projects in Europe as well as their importance in terms of budgets allocated to them by local, national, and European public authorities.³

Printed and digital editions alike incur production and maintenance costs. Yet it would be overly simplistic to reduce the distinction between these two modes of disseminating knowledge to this sole opposition. The impact of digital technology on the cultural and national heritage represented by music can provoke genuine ideological debates, as illustrated by the example of the monumental Chopin editions, where two different versions were published. Policies and marketing are closely intertwined, with increasing offerings and funding opportunities for editions. Although monumental music editions are still of great importance,

1 A. Puentes-Blanco, M. Kokole, Ph. Vendrix, M. Gembero-Ustárroz, R. Herissone, C. Troelsgård, K. Grabnar, B. Lodes, K. Schöning, & V. Vrbanic (2024). *The monumental edition in the digital age: creating a sustainable future*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09298215.2024.2373998>.

2 On this topic, see G. Born, “For a Relational Musicology: Music and Interdisciplinarity, Beyond the Practice Turn: The 2007 Dent Medal Address,” *Journal of the Royal Musical Association*, 2010, Vol. 135, No. 2, pp. 205–243.

3 For a detailed discussion of this point, see Ph. Vendrix, A. Puentes-Blanco, V. Borghetti, A. Piéjus, D. Lewis, A. Olmos, N. Marjanović, Ch. Riedo, G. Pranis, V. Parilla, & V. Vrbanic (2024). *Musicological Publications in the Digital Age: Charting a New Course*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13961016>.

they are difficult to justify because they are costly for publishers – through salaries, materials, etc. – as well as for potential buyers. Hence the need to reassess editorial methods and to redefine the objectives of new editions. From the early days of Open Access to more recent developments, the methods for rethinking the economic model and the creation of new modes of dissemination have evolved considerably. Numerous avenues nevertheless remain to be explored. Yet a crucial question persists : how can we convey the importance of these new editorial practices to concert organizers, performers, indeed the broader musical community, as well as to the world of publishing and libraries?

1.2.2. Open Access, the Cost of Print Publishing, the Market

Music editing has been reinventing itself in recent years through ambitious scholarly projects devoted to the digitization of sources. Beyond the obvious reduction in printing costs, digital editions offer unprecedented longevity and accessibility to centuries old sources, while also creating new opportunities for computational analysis. European recommendations increasingly favor sharing resources in Open Access : by adhering to these standards, research results can be made readily available to the scholarly and musical communities in a more sustainable and economical way. By offering a heritage science response to the challenges posed by the digital humanities, digital editing rethinks the very notion of authority by fostering dialogue, whether through new reconstructions of missing parts or through the exploration of the various versions of a single work. The possibility of viewing of the critical apparatus, multiple versions, links to metadata, and audio recordings

on a single web page drastically reduces editorial costs compared with those of printed editions, while the flexibility of the digital medium facilitates collaborative work. It is also possible to modify the layout of the score dynamically and to conduct analytical research within XML files using scripts. In addition to statistical analyses, that nonencoded formats cannot support, even simple variations in layout are impossible to implement on a case-by-case basis in print editions, which must adhere to standardized conventions. The possibility of editorial “customization” tailored to individual needs is therefore more economical (financially and in terms of time) than the manual modifications or pasted additions familiar to many performers. Musicians often prepare their own page layouts when working on pieces where, for example, page turns are impractical : digital media thus offer the considerable advantage of being adaptable to the needs of musicians, particularly when using tablets. These new, lowcost editions increase the potential for disseminating and reusing data, thereby contributing to the construction of a shared foundation for scientific knowledge.

This situation illustrates the persistent divide between publishers and musicians, a gap that digital editing seeks to bridge, though it remains important to keep in mind that the reception of such practices varies widely.¹

1.2.3 Why a European Approach? The Specificity of the Field of Music

Digital critical editions play a crucial role in the preservation of musical heritage and are often funded through national or European calls for proposals. Consequently, the question of their accessibility is of great importance. While Open Access poli-

¹ R. E. Scott and A. Shelley “Music Scholars and Open Access Publishing” (2022). *Faculty and Staff Publications – Milner Library*. 161. <https://ir.library.illinois-tate.edu/fpml/161>

cies remain the standard expectation for publicly funded projects, research institutions are increasingly exploring more financially viable models, such as partnerships with CCIs, in order to reduce their dependence on competitive funding.

In the context of European calls for proposals, initiatives aimed at valorizing and preserving cultural heritage are increasingly expanding to include intangible heritage, and consequently music, particularly through the use of digital twin technology.¹ The ECHOES project (European Cloud for Heritage OpEn Science), led by the European Commission and UKRI (UK Research and Innovation) from 2024 to 2029, provides a structuring framework for reimagining the place of musical editions within the broader ecosystem of heritage sciences :

ECHOES will create a digital environment that enables the digitisation of existing knowledge and the collaborative analysis of cultural heritage assets, facts, and phenomena. [...] The digital environment proposed by ECHOES will empower users to interact with, manipulate and enrich Digital Twins, fostering the creation of new, collaboratively developed scientific knowledge.²

Music presents a particularly interesting case in the context of digital twins, which must integrate multiple complementary documents to provide a faithful representation of the musical object : the reproduction of the source, most often digitized according to the IIF protocol,³ which constitutes a trace of the physical object ;

the musical encoding, which translates the musical data and makes it operational ; and finally the audio recording, which provides a sensory experience of the work.

Its semantic construction – specifically the creation of a database based on an ontology interoperable with existing repositories, implemented by many European infrastructures – would improve the accessibility to musical *corpora* through the valorization of sources. This represents a valuable tool that can generate tangible impact around research⁴ and must be considered in the design of a digital edition, particularly regarding their connections to sources and metadata. Music is indeed a universal mode of communication, capable of reaching broad audiences and reflecting a wide range of historical periods, ideologies, and religious traditions. It is therefore essential to consider the digital revolution in order to adapt the ways in which music is disseminated.

- 1 An accurate digital reconstruction of an object. For more information, see <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/articles/3-64> and <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0167923621000348?via%3Dihub>
- 2 <https://www.echoes-ecch.eu/>
- 3 Minister of Culture, « Protocole IIF — International Image Interoperability Framework », description and guidelines, <https://www.culture.gouv.fr/Thematiques/innovation-numerique/Faciliter-l-acces-aux-donnees-et-aux-contenus-culturels/ouvrir-partager-et-valoriser-les-donnees-et-les-contenus-culturels/protocole-iif-international-image-interoperability-framework>
- 4 On this topic see A. Braud, “Considering impact strategies in historical and musicological research projects.”, *Performing Royal Power in Renaissance England and France: Insights and Impact* – Le Studium Conference, Centre d’études supérieures de la Renaissance, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15118211>

This guide is primarily concerned with traditionally notated music as a scholarly editor would wish to transmit digitally. Experience with XML¹-derived publication formats naturally shapes the presentation of these methods, which are particularly well suited to notated music. Possible interactions with recorded *corpora* are also considered, as these raise specific questions that will be central to research projects conducted in partnership with the cultural and creative industries, such as the ICCARE project.

The defining feature of a digital edition lies in the way its content is made accessible and readable : it involves transforming musical information, previously confined to printed or manuscript formats and interpreted through conventions shared by performers, into structured data that can be processed by digital tools. It is therefore essential to distinguish clearly between a “digitized” edition and a “digital” edition, in order to differentiate true digital paradigms –based on encoded, interoperable files – from “fixed” formats such as pdfs. Indeed, “scholarly digital editions are scholarly editions that are guided by a digital paradigm in their theory, method and practice.”²

This process requires us to reexamine certain aspects of musicological work through the lens of data science. Digital editing is thus situated within the broader scholarly movement that has profoundly transformed the humanities and given rise to digital musicology. The traditional roles of engraver, editor, and scholarly director are being redefined : the engraver, once responsible for the transmis-

sion and interpretation of musical notation and preservation of content, must now master sophisticated digital tools for research. The editor is, in addition to scholarly work, is also responsible for the maintenance and accessibility of digital platforms to prevent obsolescence. This evolution raises questions about the nature of the artefact to be preserved in a digital edition and about the new competencies required at the intersection of musicology and the digital humanities.

2.1. Notational Tools³

2.1.1. Operating Principles

Music notation software is a tool that allows users to record musical notation on a digital platform, following transcription conventions and using practical features such as a musical interface, standardized or customizable page layouts, symbol palettes, etc. It may also provide features for working with MIDI sequences and audio mixing or production tools, often for creative purposes. While more traditional programs have largely been proprietary, there is an increasing trend toward opensource tools. While these programs have greatly contributed to the democratization of music publishing, the expertise involved remains grounded in traditional practice. The term “engraving” has gradually given way to “encoding,” reflecting a genuine shift in attitudes toward the role of musical data and the possibilities for working with it. This transition from physical to digital nonetheless respects a long-established historical practice with norms and conventions that are essential

1 *Extensible Markdown Language*: a general purpose markup language for describing data.

2 P. Sahle, “What is a Scholarly Digital Edition?”, in *Digital Scholarly Editing: Theories and Practices*, ed. J. M. Driscoll and E. Pierazzo, Cambridge, Open Book Publishers, 2016, pp. 19–39, <https://books.openedition.org/obp/3397?lang=fr>

3 This guide was finalized during the first semester of 2025 and therefore reflects the perspectives of that period.

for maintaining the visual quality and integrity of editions. Current challenges in Open Science and data analysis, however, call into question the relevance of these software tools, which often focus more on the symbolic reproduction of a musical work than on its semantic content and a proper digital description.

In general, music editing software consists of (1) a user interface, (2) a software engine, (3) integration, export, and playback modules, and (4) additional resources such as sound libraries fonts, etc. The programming languages used depend on the production methods of the developers or companies involved, whether proprietary or open source. They may employ a combination of programming languages and libraries specific to virtual instruments or music notation. The widespread adoption of MusicXML as the standard export format, along with the MIDI¹ standard, has significantly influenced the architecture of many systems, with internal formats often imitating the structure of these two standards for practical reasons. For example, .sib (Sibelius) or .mus (Finale) file formats draw heavily on MusicXML though they still incorporate software specific features. Similarly, the .mxl (MuseScore) format is essentially a compressed MusicXML file.

Numerous resources provide guidance for developing proper habits in music transcription.² However the technical constraints and certain software features can influence or even limit the editor's work and vision. These constraints are often related to the exclusively "symbolic" tradition of music notation ; different forms of musical notation require specific training, whether for early music (10th to 16th centuries) or for 20th and 21st century repertoires, all of which rely on complex

semiotic codes. For example, the characteristics of liturgical monody led the Gregorio³ project adopted a variant of ABC notation (*gabc*) along with a TeX-based visual representation in a customized style. While such examples illustrate the diversity of principles and digital resources currently in use, they also raise important questions regarding interoperability and data reusability, while requiring substantial technical expertise. Challenges include the resolution of certain ligatures, passages in blackened notation, changes rhythmic nomenclature, mensuration, key signatures, clefs... Consideration must also be given to various tablature notations – German, Spanish, French, Italian – frequently used for period instruments. For 20th century music, the unique symbols used by composers complicates the systematization of musical encoding. Editors must therefore often compromise between data interoperability and the fidelity of visual rendering.

When dealing with early, nonEuropean, or other specialized music notations, editors often "alter" the file structure (through additional fonts, hidden measures, etc.) or rely on more restrictive solutions such as modern transcription. While the former compromises the integrity of the format, the latter entails reinterpreting the meaning of the original notation. These methods have frequently been criticized in comparison with approaches that are more respectful of musical semantics such as those exemplified by the MEI standard.

Editorial guidelines also concern the declaration of metadata, a fundamental aspect within the realm open science and data reuse. Focused primarily on the visual aspects of music notation, most editing software unfortunately pro-

1 Musical Instrument Digital Interface

2 E. Gould, *Behind bars : the definitive guide to notation*, London, Faber Music, 2011.

3 See <https://gregorio-project.github.io/>

vides only limited options to editors. In some cases, exporting via pivot formats such as MusicXML fails to preserve the full range of software-specific metadata, significantly complicating the editorial translation process. To guarantee longterm accessibility, it therefore seems more reliable to adopt a preservation strategy based on the MEI standard, similar to the use of LaTeX, a text editor widely used in academia that relies on plain text files with tags to define the structure and content of a document.

2.1.2. Main Software

A major issue emerged early in 2025 : the developers of the two most widely used notation programs – Finale and Sibelius – announced that these applications would no longer be updated. This raises the question of how long Sibelius and Finale, as well as the files created by them, will remain usable. Nevertheless, it remains essential to provide a comprehensive list of the main existing notation software:

Finale: Music notation software for Windows and macOS, developed and published by MakeMusic, with French translation and distribution handled by IPE Music (fig. 1). Known for its high-quality graphic output, Finale is proprietary software, which means it requires a paid subscription.¹ It supports export in a wide range of formats (pdf, MusicXML, etc.), but not MEI. In December 2024, however, MakeMusic announced that updates for Finale would be discontinued, rendering the software obsolete within a few months ; it is therefore no longer a longterm solution.

fig. 1 : *Wen, ich mit Menschen*, Johannes Brahms ; overview of Finale workspace

The screenshot shows the Finale software interface. At the top, there are playback controls including a measure counter (1|1|0000) and a time display (00:00:00.000). Below this is a toolbar with various editing tools. The main workspace displays a musical score for 'Wen, ich mit Menschen' by Johannes Brahms. The score is in G major and 4/4 time, with a tempo marking of 'Andante con moto ed anima.' and a metronome marking of '♩ = 80'. The score is arranged for Baritone and Piano. The lyrics are in German. The score is displayed in a two-staff format (Baritone and Piano) with lyrics in German. The interface includes a toolbar with various editing tools, a playback controls panel at the top right, and a vertical toolbar on the left. The score is titled 'Andante con moto ed anima.' and includes the tempo marking '♩ = 80'. The lyrics are: 'Wenn ich mit Menschen und mit sa - gen könn - te und En - gels - zungen re - det - e, und hät - te der Lie - be nicht, so wär ich ein tö - nend hät - te al - len Glau - Erz, o - der ei - ne - klin - gen - de Schel - le. Und wenn ... ich weis - hät - te der Lie - dolce Und wenn'.

¹ <https://www.finalemusic.com/blog/>

2. MUSIC EDITING AND THE DIGITAL REVOLUTION

Sibelius: Notation software distributed by Avid, which also requires a paid subscription¹ (fig. 2). It produces scores with highdefinition graphics and supports numerous export formats. File sharing is facilitated by these export formats, particularly MusicXML, and the downloadable plugin <sibmei> allows users to export files in MEI format.² Sibelius also supports the editing of historic and modern tablature. When used with PhotoScore (an optical music recognition tool for Sibelius), it can convert pdf scores into Sibelius files. As with Finale, the future of Sibelius appears uncertain : several key positions have recently been eliminated, suggesting that the software may soon be discontinued, or at least no longer updated.

fig. 2: Sonata n° 5, Alexandre Scriabine ; overview of Sibelius workspace

Dorico: Developed by Steinberg, Dorico has emerged as a potential new standard.³ Supported by a dynamic development team and a steadily growing user community, Dorico allows export to MIDI, pdf, and MusicXML. Export to MEI is not yet available (fig. 3).

fig. 3: overview of Dorico workspace

1 <https://www.avid.com/sibelius/>

2 <https://music-encoding.org/>

3 <https://www.steinberg.net/fr/dorico/new-features/>

MuseScore: Open-source software application designed for transcribing and editing musical scores.¹ Its user interface is similar to that of Sibelius (fig. 4). MuseScore supports more than fifty languages and is available for PC, Macintosh, and Linux, as well as through mobile applications for Android and iOS. It also hosts an online library of musical scores maintained by an active community eager to invest in musical encoding. MuseScore's primary advantage for editing music is its ability to export directly to MEI ; since last year, the program also supports importing MEI files in order to view them graphically.

LilyPond: LilyPond is an open-source software affiliated with the GNU project (fig. 5). Developed in 1996 by HanWen Nienhuys and Jan Nieuwenhuizen, LilyPond is textbased and therefore lacks a graphical interface for real-time score visualization : the score is generated only after all the input has been processed. The LilyPond language, like TeX, includes extensive commands to represent articulations, dynamics, meter, and other notational elements, making it well suited to engraving complex repertoires, from medieval notation to contemporary scores. The ability to integrate Scheme code within a LilyPond file also facilitates algorithmic composition. The chief strength of LilyPond is its capacity to produce graphically meticulous scores, in contrast to the more mechanical appearance often generated by computers.²

fig. 4: overview of MuseScore workspace

fig. 5: LilyPond site

1 <https://musescore.org/fr>

2 <https://lilypond.org/>

Noteflight: Unlike the softwares described above, Noteflight is accessible directly through a web browser, thus does not requiring installation (**fig. 6**). Although it supports export to MusicXML, it remains comparatively limited relative to its competitors.¹

fig. 6: overview of Noteflight workspace

Programs designed for viewing and editing tablature for lute and related historical instruments include LuteScribe, TabCode, and Fronimo, as well as Gregorio for neumatic notation. For XXI^e music, composers increasingly work directly with image-editing software such as Illustrator or Photoshop, an approach that diverges significantly from processing encoded data and metadata. Furthermore, despite the diversity of these programs, some open source, others proprietary, all of them feature export systems robust enough to enable the exchange of musical content without substantially altering the files. These tools make it possible both to produce highquality data encoding and to share data in accordance with FAIR

principles. They allow users to capture musical data by integrating personalized parameters while remaining open to other possibilities through Linked Open Data, a method designed to facilitate the sharing of interconnected data.²

2.2. Music Encoding

2.2.1. Formats

Each program, whether proprietary or not, generates its own file type: Finale creates .mus files, Sibelius .sib files, ... etc. In order to facilitate sharing essential data with the community, developers have consistently sought to provide export formats that enable file sharing among users working in different environments. Most of these programs now offer several export options, including MusicXML, pdf, midi, image formats, and MEI either directly within the application or through plugins.

2.2.1.1. MusicXML

Although pdf format remains widely used for commercial publishing and printing, open export formats such as MusicXML enable computational analysis and ensure data interoperability. They are therefore of clear interest to both musicologists and publishers, who can use them to share files easily. Based on the universal XML textual format for transmitting and disseminating data, MusicXML is a structured, hierarchical, and extensible language that nevertheless has one drawback – it is verbose : one measure may correspond to several hundred lines of code. The vast majority of the software discussed above supports native export in MusicXML, making it a widely accessible and high-quality standard. However

¹ <https://www.noteflight.com/>

² To understand the significance of *linked open data* and the possibilities it offers for connecting *corpora*, see : <https://lod-cloud.net/clouds/lod-cloud.svg>

some data and metadata can be omitted during export to MusicXML format, which necessitates additional work on the resulting files. It is therefore essential to pay close attention to the original encoding upon which the data export processes depend. Good encoding practices greatly facilitate the overall editing process by avoiding unnecessary accumulation of elements that could compromise the encoding, for example, an excessive use of personalized or unconventional graphics.

2.2.1.2. MEI

MEI (Music Encoding Initiative) is an encoding format designed to support the semantic and scholarly use of musical data. It builds on MusicXML format and is directly derived from TEI (Text Encoding Initiative), one of the earliest specialized text formats, created in 1987 for the critical and diplomatic editing of texts. MEI was introduced in 1999–2000 as an open source format for music encoding that can generate PDF and SVG files (viewable through online rendering tools such as VexFlow and later Verovio), as well as MIDI files. Similar to TEI, a single master file can now serve for both online publication (webXML) and a printed score. The strength of encoding, and the MEI format in particular, for music editing lies in the coexistence of two complementary dimensions : a graphical output for visualization of the score, particularly useful when working from manuscripts, and a logical transcription of musical information into code, which can thus be subjected to analytical processes and networked parametrically (fig. 7). These elements are organized logically and structured clearly, making MEI more suitable for processing musical data than the XML format. Indeed, XML requires a separate line for each descriptive element, whereas MEI consolidates all this information within a single line. This economy of notation translates into an economy of storage, thanks to a more compact format (fig. 8):

fig. 7: a Renaissance polyphony encoded in MEI and its graphic output, both visible within a single interface.

fig. 8: the same passage, shown in XML format on the left and MEI format on the right.

fig. 9: *Avava Inouva, Idi* (modern Kabyle song) shown alongside ; exported in .mei format with the text integrated.¹

The figure shows a musical score for the song 'Avava Inouva, Idi'. The score is in G major (one sharp) and 4/4 time. It consists of three measures, numbered 9, 10, and 11. The lyrics are: 'Txi - lek el - li yin ta-burt a ___ Va- val - nou-va a ___ Va- val'. Below the score, the MEI XML code is displayed. Three arrows point from the lyrics to the corresponding XML elements: 'Txi' is linked to `<syl xml:id="m-47" con="d" wordpos="1">Txi</syl>`, 'lek' is linked to `<syl xml:id="m-49" wordpos="2">lek</syl>`, and 'el' is linked to `<syl xml:id="m-51" con="d" wordpos="1">el</syl>`.

fig. 10: FRBR conceptual model.²

Several tools are available to export files encoded in MEI. Although Sibelius is no longer actively developed, it remains widely used in the editorial community. Exporting to MEI is straightforward via the Sib>MEI plugin developed by the MEI community and available online,³ along with the necessary installation instructions. However, it appears that the preferred software for digital music editing is now MuseScore, as it allows direct export to MEI from the application without the need for a plugin. Data preservation is generally satisfactory for traditionally notated repertoires, and it can also accommodate oral music traditions by enabling clear visualization of textual elements (fig. 9, opposite).

MEI format also allows for the inclusion of a critical apparatus, potential variants, and an extensive set of metadata within its header, which can, for example, integrate the FRBR model (Functional Requirements for Bibliographic Records) (fig. 10) to establish more precise connections with the library world.⁴

One of the most important features of MEI format is its ability to designate noteworthy elements using the attribute `<xml:id>`, which allows each element to be uniquely identified. These elements can then be linked to sources and audio recordings through thesauruses and reference systems. For certain notational symbols, such as those used for *musica ficta*, it is even possible to automate some necessary interventions in the code to ensure a standardized visualization. A short

1 See S. Martin de Guise. *La MEI (Music Encoding Initiative) : un standard au service de la musique kabyle*. Iles d'Imesli, 2013. hal-02948837

2 B. B. Tillett (Library of Congress) : "What is FRBR ? A Conceptual Model for the Bibliographic Universe," published in *Technicalities*, vol. 25, no 5 (September 2003).

3 <https://github.com/music-encoding/sibmei>

4 For more information, see : <https://music-encoding.org/guidelines/v3/content/frbr.html>

Python¹ script can be used to enrich or correct files, provided they have been properly prepared in advance. Numerous editorial projects already rely on this format.² Because it is user friendly, has an active community, and can illuminate both musical heritage and its associated data, MEI has become the preferred solution for digital music editing.

2.2.1.3. HumDrum

Humdrum is a suite of tools and resources for computational music analysis, created by David Huron in 1995 and maintained by Craig Sapp at the Center for Computer Assisted Research in the Humanities. Its syntax provides a data structure within which users define specific interpretive schemes with a level of complexity appropriate to a given corpus. The ****kern** music notation format is used regularly in various projects³; it allows for the representation of basic elements inherent to Western music, such as pitch and duration. However unlike many other music formats, “humdrum is not limited to traditional Western notation, but rather affords the study of nonWestern, vernacular, or avantgarde musics, as any type of musical feature, data, or metadata to be easily encoded in the same place.”⁴ This flexibility makes it possible to develop custom tools to address specific musicolog-

ical questions by encoding directly in MEI and using a compatible viewer, such as the Verovio Humdrum Viewer (fig. 11). The Humdrum encoding format is ideal for the analysis of large datasets due to the flexibility of the tools it offers.

fig. 11: *Die Kunst der Fuge, Contrapunctus 1, a 4.*, J-S Bach ; humdrum visualization using the Verovio Humdrum Viewer.⁵

2.2.1.4. PDF

Although formats such as XML or MEI enhance analytical possibilities, many users predominately use PDF. The pdf format is central to the work of commercial

- 1 Python is a general-purpose programming language that is suitable not only for software or web development but also for computational operations on *corpora*, as is the case here.
- 2 For example, *Gesualdo Online* and *Corpus Monodicum*.
- 3 One recent example is the encoding of the first Chopin editions, C. S. Sapp & M. Konik (2025). *pl-wnjfc/humdrum-chopin-first-editions: Humdrum digital scores of Chopin first editions* (v1.0.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14879352>
- 4 N. Condit-Schultz & C. Arthur. (2019). *humdrumR: a New Take on an Old Approach to Computational Musicology*. Proceedings of the 20th International Society for Music Information Retrieval Conference, 715-722. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3527910>
- 5 <https://www.humdrum.org/>

publishers as well as performing musicians, who value it for its ease of use and the ability to make handwritten annotations on tablets. Companies such as Newzik¹ have also recognized the value of a tool that for annotating and organizing scores, including in ensemble work.

It is important to note, however, that the mere conversion of a manuscript into a .pdf file does not constitute a true digital edition, since it does not allow one to take advantage of the intrinsic properties encoded in the file, despite its satisfactory graphical output.

2.2.2. Metadata

One of the main challenges of digital music editing is creating a functional and enduring link between metadata and musical data. Various encoding processes make it possible to add a wide range of metadata and to attach them to targeted elements : MEI (for music encoding) and TEI and LaTeX (for text) are particularly well suited to these purposes.

To consider the essential metadata for ensuring the quality of an encoded file, it is first necessary to refer to the MEI *Guidelines*.² Metadata are gathered in the header,³ which provides a comprehensive description of the digital file and must *a minima* allow for the creation of an appropriate bibliographic citation. This typically includes the file title, information about the source from which the electronic document was encoded, and details regarding the MEI elements used. The header is structured into three major sections within a <fileDesc> : <titleStmt>, <resp

stmt>, and <sourceDesc>. <titleStmt> contains information on the title, subtitle, and composer. <respStmt> identifies the editors, and <sourceDesc> holds information related to the source. A recommended best practice is to consult established reference frameworks when completing the header to maximize the interoperability of the edition. MEI headers that contain URIs can then be directly linked to the manuscript via Verovio, as is the case with *Beethovens Werkstatt* (fig. 12).

fig. 12 : Autograph op. 111., Ludwig van Beethoven ; visualization of the source and the MEI header.⁴

1 <https://newzik.com/fr/>

2 We refer to the following page within this section : <https://music-encoding.org/guidelines/v4/content/metadata.html>

3 Term referring to the file header in which all metadata are declared, distinct from the “body,” which contains all the descriptive elements of the music.

4 <https://demo.beethovens-werkstatt.de/index.html>

2. MUSIC EDITING AND THE DIGITAL REVOLUTION

It is, however, important to consider the purpose of the edition when deciding whether to integrate metadata directly within the encoded files, or whether their volume and complexity necessitate creating a relational database. The advantage of MEI lies in its ability to consolidate a large amount of information within a single file that provides access to metadata and a highquality graphical representation. Some research projects will indeed favor files rich in metadata through links established with reference systems (VIAF, Wikidata, Geonames, Getty AAT, and MIMO, for instruments), while others may prefer a more streamlined approach to facilitate seamless analysis across large *corpora*. In the case of music, it is a recommended best practice to register metadata with RISM, regardless of historical period. A RISM ID^I allows for the linking of key information, including the type of source, the individuals who edited or annotated it, and the holding institution (fig. 13).

fig. 13 : *De double duel*, Jean Servin ; export in .mei format, header incorporating metadata connected to established reference systems.


```
1 <?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8" ?>
2 <mei xml:id="m-1" meiversion="4.0.1" xmlns="http://www.music-encoding.org/ns/mei" xmlns:xlink="http://www.w3.org/1999/xlink">
3 <meiHead xml:id="m-2">
4 <fileDesc xml:id="m-3">
5 <titleStmt xml:id="m-4">
6 <title xml:id="m-14" type="main">Ce double duel</title>
7 <title xml:id="m-15" type="subordinate">Premier livre de chansons 1578</title>
8 <title type="subtitle">A Digital Edition</title>
9 <composer xml:id="m-16">
10 <persName auth="VIAF" auth.uri="https://viaf.org/viaf/47029401/">Jean Servin</persName>
11 </composer>
12 <respStat xml:id="m-22">
13 <persName xml:id="JP" role="editor">James Porter</persName>
14 <persName xml:id="MS" role="encoder">Michael Swithinbank</persName>
15 <persName xml:id="VB" role="proofreader" auth="orcid" auth.uri="https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5618-8602/">Vincent Besson</persName>
16 <persName xml:id="DN" role="proofreader">David Nzavaret</persName>
17 </respStat>
18 <corpName>
19 <name>Centre national de la recherche scientifique</name>
20 <abbr>CNRS</abbr>
21 </corpName>
22 <name>UMR 7323, Centre d'études supérieures de la Renaissance</name>
23 <abbr>CESR</abbr>
24 </corpName>
25 <name>Ricercar Lab</name>
26 <address>
27 <street>59 rue Néricault-Destouches</street>
28 <postBox>BP 12056</postBox>
29 <postCode>37020</postCode>
30 <settlement>Tours</settlement>
31 <country>France</country>
32 </address>
33 </corpName>
34 </corpName>
35 </respStat>
36 <funder>
37 <corpName auth="ROR" auth.uri="https://ror.org/03cv31o28/">Centre d'études supérieures de la Renaissance</corpName>
38 <corpName auth="ROR" auth.uri="https://ror.org/0302b467/">British Academy</corpName>
39 </funder>
40 </titleStmt>
41 <pubStmt xml:id="m-24">
42 <availability xml:id="m-25">
43 <useRestrict xml:id="m-26">© 2024 Ricercar Lab</useRestrict>
44 </availability>
45 </pubStmt>
46 <sourceDesc>
47 <source recordtype="c">
48 <bibl>
49 <composer>
50 <persName auth="VIAF" auth.uri="https://viaf.org/viaf/47029401/">Jean Servin</persName>
51 </composer>
52 <title type="main">Premier livre de chansons nouvelles à quatre, 1578</title>
53 </bibl>
54 <publisher>
55 <persName auth="VIAF" auth.uri="https://viaf.org/viaf/830004/#Pesnot,_Charles,_15...-1584">Charles Pesnot</persName>
56 </publisher>
57 <imprint>
58 <date>1578</date>
59 <settlement auth="Geonames" auth.uri="https://www.geonames.org/2996944/Lyon.html">Lyon</settlement>
60 </imprint>
61 <biblScope>
62 <num label="page">p. 9</num>
63 <num label="workposition">11</num>
64 </biblScope>
65 <identifier auth="RISM" auth.uri="https://opac.rism.info/search?id=990059232">RISM A/I S 2838</identifier>
66 <relatedItem>
67 <bibl>
68 <ref target="https://stimbuecher.digitale-sammlungen.de/view?id=bsb00089921L"></ref>
69 </bibl>
70 </relatedItem>
71 </source>
72 </sourceDesc>
```

I For more information on this topic, see <https://rism.info/community/how-to-cite-rism.html>

It is also possible to rely on the FRBR model, a conceptual framework for bibliographic data that organizes works and sources. This model can be integrated into the header¹ to facilitate communication with libraries – which constitute the majority of *corpora* – and their standards. Additionally, use of the Semantic Web enables edited music to be incorporated into European projects such as the forthcoming European Cloud for Cultural Heritage, which is based on the CIDOC CRM² ontology and its LRMoo extension (itself grounded in the FRBR model).³

Although this constitutes a relatively late stage in a digital editing project, it is important to consider the interoperability of the corpus from the outset to ensure its effective dissemination. This objective is crucial for the visibility of our digital music editions as well as for musicology.

2.3. Tools for Editing and File Conversion

2.3.1 The Viewer : Verovio

Verovio is an online tool that displays MEI files automatically in score format, using SVG (Scalable Vector Graphics). This viewer is developed by the RISM Digital Center with the support of the Swiss National Science Foundation. Verovio is written in standard C++ and can be compiled either as a standalone command-line tool or as JavaScript. Beyond simple score visualization, its main advantage is

its accuracy in preserving the metadata of the original MusicXML file, as well as its ability to edit and correct MEI files in real time.

Despite its user-friendly design and the immediacy of visual rendering, thorough preparation of files prior to MEI export remains essential to ensure high-quality output. Verovio do not yet support all aspects of advanced notation, in particular the graphical features required for the transcription of medieval repertoires and the symbols used in contemporary music. Particular care must also be taken with works containing text, ensuring the precise alignment of syllables with their corresponding notes.

2.3.2 MEIFriend

MEIFriend is an editor for musical encodings hosted at the University of Music and Performing Arts Vienna, in Austria. It is a browser-based application that uses Verovio as a viewer. It enables users to edit and validate MEI files directly within the web browser. This platform is particularly well suited for realtime visualization of any modifications made to the MEI code.⁴

2.3.3 OCR/OMR

One of the most significant recent innovations in music editing is the development of OCR (Optical Character Recognition) and OMR (Optical Music Recognition) technologies, which are increasingly supported by artificial intelligence.

1 On this topic, see <https://music-encoding.org/guidelines/v4/content/metadata.html#FRBR>

2 For more information, see : <https://cidoc-crm.org/>

3 For more information, see T. Bottini, A. Braud, M. Gurrieri et K. Roger : *Approches de la complétion des Headers MEI par les GT1>2 du Consortium-HN Musica2*: https://github.com/Amlenth/consortium-musica2-gt2-ontologies/blob/main/modules/livrables/mei_headers_gt1_gt2/index.md

4 On mei-friend, see : <https://mei-friend.mdw.ac.at>

The U.I. for Computing Research at the University of Alicante in Spain¹ has made substantial developments in OMR, while in France, CollabScore was one of the first projects to employ this technology. Its OMR system combines deep learning with tools for modeling music notation: “The system analyzes the image of the score and, drawing on its knowledge of musical notation, is able to produce a complete representation of the recognized score while verifying its internal consistency.”² The DMOS OMR is thus capable of distinguishing parts from voices, as well as visualizing the text and linking it to corresponding staves (fig. 14):

fig 14 : two examples : voice identification across multiple staves (l) and text recognition (r).³

For early music, Aruspix,⁴ developed by Laurent Pugin in connection with the Marenzio critical edition and in collaboration with the MEI community, aims to maximize interoperability. Aruspix allows users to superimpose two copies of the same work, to identify the symbols used in historical compositions via an OMR algorithm based on hidden Markov models, and it supports *collatio* of different sources.

Audiveris,⁵ a free, fast, and powerful OMR tool, is a more accessible application used by MuseScore. It is recommended for work on sources with traditional notation, presented clearly – for example the *corpora* in resources such as IMSLP – and can serve as a solid starting point for employing such tools in a digital edition.⁶

The use of OMR tools highlights the importance of decisions made by the scholarly editor, decisions that extend beyond philological debates to encompass broader ethical considerations, the urgency of which has increased with the proliferation of artificial intelligence and its social and environmental impact.

2.3.4. Converters: Meico and MEI Garage

Encoding is useful beyond visualization and metadata referencing. Depending on the project, it may also be advantageous to export an edition in various formats,

1 C. Penarrubia, C. Garrido-Munoz, J.J. Valero-Mas, and J. Calvo-Zaragoza, “Efficient Notation Assembly in Optical Music Recognition”, in Proc. of the 24th Int. Society for Music Information Retrieval Conf., Milan, Italy, 2023.

2 <https://collabscore.github.io/collabscore.html>

3 For more information, see <https://collabscore.github.io/omr.html>

4 <https://www.aruspix.net/index.html>

5 For more information, see <https://github.com/Audiveris/audiveris>

6 A complete list of resources on OMR can be consulted via this link : <https://github.com/OMR-Research/omr-research.github.io/blob/master/OMR-Related-Research.bib>

such as an audio file or even a REST API (Application Programming Interface). One of the most effective tools for working with MEI files is meico, a program written entirely in Java. Although MEI has become a standard for digital music editions, processing MEI-encoded music is not a trivial task, and many application scenarios rely on more established and efficient formats. Meico implements methods to convert MEI data into other formats, making MEI encodings accessible to a wider range of applications.¹

MEI Garage² is another tool that facilitates common tasks such as converting between formats like MIDI, as well as modifying MEI files within a corpus. Its clear and user-friendly interface makes it accessible even to beginners.

2.4. Copyright and Legal Concerns

2.4.1. The Role and Visibility of the Editor ; Collaborative Processes

Encoding scores allows for the inclusion of metadata, such as the roles of editor, engraver, and reviewer. The role of collaborators in music editing raises fundamental questions about the boundaries between individual contributions and collective efforts. How should one distinguish between a collaborator and an editor or commentator? For example, should someone who corrects individual notes or articulations be considered a collaborator, or does their role fall under editorial assistance?

MEI format offers a partial solution to these questions through `<respStmt>`,³ included in the header discussed above, which allows for listing all contributors who have worked on the edition (fig. 15) :

These tools are particularly important in the context of online music editions that allow for the completion of missing voices.⁴ This distinction carries significant implications for how contributions are identified in music editing and in musicology more broadly. Careful attention is required to ensure that each contributor's input to a digital edition is properly credited. The use of identifier systems such as ORCID provides an additional means of acknowledging authors' work.

fig. 15 : *Leve le cœur*, Jean Servin ; excerpt from the MEI header, specifically `<respStmt>`.

```

1  <?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8" ?>
2  <mei xml:id="m-1" meiversion="4.0.1" xmlns="http://www.music-encoding.org/ns/mei" xmlns:xlink="http://www.w3.org/1999/xlink">
3    <meiHead xml:id="m-2">
4      <fileDesc xml:id="m-3">
5        <titleStmt xml:id="m-4">
6          <title xml:id="m-14" type="main">Leve le cœur (Les Commandemens de Dieu)</title>
7          <title xml:id="m-15" type="subordinate">Second livre de chansons 1578</title>
8          <title type="subtitle">A Digital Edition</title>
9          <composer xml:id="m-16">
10           <persName auth="VIAF" auth.uri="https://viaf.org/viaf/47029401/">Jean Servin</persName>
11         </composer>
12         <respStmt xml:id="m-22">
13           <persName xml:id="JP" role="editor">James Porter</persName>
14           <persName xml:id="MS" role="encoder">Mickael Swithinbank</persName>
15           <persName xml:id="VB" role="proofreader" auth="orcid" auth.uri="https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5618-8602">Vincent Besson</persName>
16           <persName xml:id="DN" role="proofreader" auth="orcid" auth.uri="https://orcid.org/0009-0000-2178-2492">David Nivarlet</persName>
17         </respStmt>
18       </titleStmt>
19       <name>Centre national de la recherche scientifique</name>
20       <abbr>CNRS</abbr>
21       <corpName>
22         <name>UMR 7322, Centre d'études supérieures de la Renaissance</name>
23         <abbr>CESR</abbr>
24       </corpName>
25       <corpName>
26         <name>RicercaLab</name>
27         <address>
28           <street>59 rue Néricault-Destouches</street>
29           <postBox>BP 12050</postBox>
30           <postCode>37020</postCode>
31           <settlement>Tours</settlement>
32           <country>France</country>
33         </address>
34       </corpName>
35     </meiHead>
  
```

1 <https://github.com/cemfi/meico?tab=readme-ov-file>

2 <https://meigarage.edirom.de/>

3 Abbreviation for : Responsibility Statement

4 As with, for example, *Gesualdo Online*.

Edited works serve as valuable pedagogical tools, providing performers and students with informed interpretations of the repertoire. It is not uncommon for editions to result from collaborations between researchers, musicians, and experienced engineers, as well as master's or doctoral students engaged in research projects. These students may initially train in digital editing practices before applying this experience to their own musical and scholarly projects ; it is therefore essential to credit their contributions properly, since such collaboration can be beneficial for their future careers. Depositing projects under a Creative Commons license such as CC BYNC-SA 4.0 provides legal protection for the editions¹ : the author must always be credited (BY), use must be noncommercial (NC), and derivative editions are permitted (SA), a provision particularly well suited to critical editions.

Highquality editions leave a lasting impact on the field of musicology : notable examples include the *Josquin* Project, one of the first digital music editions, as well as the *CRIM*, *Duchemin*, and *Gesualdo* projects.² These editions also directly influence performers' choices and the accessibility of works, thereby shaping concert programming and the broader music industry. Moreover, the role of experience in developing knowledge and understanding of repertoires cannot be overstated. An editor's or collaborator's familiarity with a given repertoire often enables them to give works that might initially seem less accessible the attention they merit, thus broadening the horizons of performers and audiences. It is also important to clearly distinguish the roles of composer, editor, and arranger ; these considerations should be addressed from the outset of an editorial project to ensure that the processes that led to the final edition are transparent.

2.4.2. Musical Editions, Digital Editions, and Rights

Financial models for musical publishing depend on the correlation of many factors, the most fundamental of which is undoubtedly the scholarly quality of the edition. Beyond musicological expertise, the integration of contributors into networks for the dissemination of research results plays a crucial role in the production and diffusion of critical editions. Some institutions, such as the CMBV (Centre de Musique Baroque de Versailles), operate under commercial publishing agreements. Revenue generated from the sale of critical editions supports employment of a dedicated editorial team. While this model effectively sustains both scholarly excellence and cost management, it raises questions about data accessibility at a time when Open Access is increasingly regarded as the ideal standard. The CMBV addresses this issue through a hybrid model : some scores are made freely available online, while others must be rented for use in performances. It remains difficult to envision how monumental editions might break away from print format, as these editions still comprise extensive volumes encompassing the complete works of a composer, without even considering their high production costs :

We can observe, though, that the creation of full digital editions within monumental series is still experimental and in progress. [...] In most of the cases considered here the move to digital editions would not yet be possible in a near future. [...] Skills for music editors in the digital era include for instance mastery of different music edition software and even programming knowledge, but there is a gap between musicological curricula in many universities around the world and the technological skill

1 See : <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/4.0/deed.fr>

2 <https://ricercadatalab.cesr.univ-tours.fr/fr/projects/>

set needed for producing digital critical editions. If we think about the enormous amount of repertoire that has been edited in monumental collections, there is a need for visibility and accessibility to that information.¹

When designing an edition, it is therefore essential to consider the commercial strategy to be adopted. Selling products that stem directly from publicly funded research may appear problematic. At the same time, Open Access depends heavily on the financial support allocated to research projects. For the future of critical editing, it is thus necessary to envision alternative and complementary funding models by developing strategies that encourage philanthropic support alongside traditional academic funding measures.

2.4.3. Recorded Music and the CCIs

An important consideration in discussions of digital musical editions concerns the omnipresence of the majors, multinational groups responsible for publishing and distributing a large share of recordings. These companies frequently claim, rightly or wrongly, that the audience for music is shrinking, thereby perpetuating a system in which musicians are often required to finance their own recordings and even their distribution. Within this context, popular music tends to set market standards, which inevitably shape both publishing practices and music education.

Similarly, established publishing houses often avoid offering initial payments for the publication of editions, citing profitability concerns. Government subsidies nevertheless enable certain institutions to build inhouse editorial and

publishing teams, thereby overcoming these challenges through internal production. In the United Kingdom, the discussion remains nuanced, with no definitive stance in favor of one model over another. European Union funding, by contrast, mandates Open Access, while still permitting paid promotion in certain cases.

A hybrid model such as that developed by the CMBV is particularly compelling : public funding is directed toward the music industry to create an economic model that no longer relies solely on commercial revenue. It is therefore essential to consider the relationship between sources, musical encoding, and recordings in order to produce digital twins – composed of these three interconnected elements – of our *corpora* and to make them accessible to the public. The integration of audio also represents a major challenge for any new edition, as it requires finding a legal balance between Open Access policies and the commercialization of editions and recordings.

¹ A. Puentes-Blanco, M. Kokole, Ph. Vendrix, M. Gembero-Ustárroz, R. Herissonne, et al.. *The monumental edition in the digital age: creating a sustainable future*. *Journal of New Music Research*, 2024, pp. 1-13. ff 10.1080/09298215.2024.2373998ff.

3.1. Musical Data

3.1.1. Notational Diversity : Pedagogical and Historical Tools

The encoding process involves numerous tasks, ranging from score analysis to acquiring the technical skills required to complete the editorial work. While it is difficult to precisely predict future technological developments, artificial intelligence will likely provide a range of tools to facilitate score encoding, including for complex examples, and enable the automation of exporting MEI and TEI files, etc.

Beyond the importance of first gaining a basic understanding of the XML format, necessary for accurately translating various notations and understanding how data is structured, it is equally important not to overlook the symbolic dimension inherent in properly understanding a score – for instance particular cases such as neumes (minimAE¹) or tablature notations. A dedicated module, ReTab, was thus developed by Ailin Arjmand and Reza Seyedi specifically for encoding tablatures in MEI. It adopts certain elements from the Common Music Notation (CMN) module while adding specialized features to meet the unique requirements of encoding tablature.² For music composed after 1945, relatively few encoding projects have been undertaken so far,³ partly due to the challenges of transcribing symbolic notation into MEI. While it is possible to include URIs

linking to images or various reference repositories within an MEI file, doing so can compromise the semantic quality of the encoding. Consequently, it becomes more difficult to perform analytical operations based on these enriched encodings or to interpret the symbols semiotically, beyond their mere existence as images.

Given the variability of notations and practices, it is important to establish an editorial model that is neutral and comprehensive from the outset. The model employed by the Polish Music Heritage project⁴ appears to meet this requirement : the resulting MEI score is accessible online via an SVG export that can be viewed with various presentation options and can be exported in other formats, while its metadata are linked to multiple reference systems (RISM, Wikidata, etc.). The source is also made viewable through the IIIF protocol, allowing any rectangular fragment to be directly addressed via an URL. These three key components –IIIF-based source digitization, metadata interoperability, and smooth MEI file visualization – form a solid foundation for launching a digital music edition.

1 For more information, see <https://vitry.org/actualites/geneseduprojet/>

2 For more information, see A. Arjmand & R. Seyedi (2025). *A Step Forward in Lute Tablature Studies with MEI.Tablature*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15688154>

3 An interesting project to follow in the coming years is the complete edition of B. A. Zimmermann's works, carried out by the Berlin-Brandenburgischen Akademie der Wissenschaften and l'Akademie der Wissenschaften und der Literatur Mainz between 2016 and 2040. For more information, see <https://www.zimmermann-gesamtausgabe.de/edition/werke.html>

4 See <https://polish.musicsources.pl/en/>

fig. 16: *Missa pulchra es – Kyrie*, Giovanni Francesco Anerio ; visualization of the work on polish-

Polish Digital Scores

Giovanni Francesco Anerio
1569-1630
CPDL IMSLP RISM VIAF Wikidata
Wikipedia Worldcat

Wawel Cathedral, Cracow
PL-Kk: Kk.I.83

Missa pulchra es
Kyrie

Cantus I. Altus I. Tenor I. Bassus I. Cantus II. Altus II. Tenor II. Bassus II

Ky - ri - e e - ley - fon Ky - ri - e e - ley - fon Ky - ri - e e - ley - fon Ky - ri - e

scores.org.

3.1.2. Essential Signs versus Complementary Signs

The question of essential signs – both semiotic and visual – arises at the very earliest stages of studying a corpus to be edited. How can one convey the richness of the sources through the encoding process, identifying the fundamental informa-

tion that must be represented, and, to some extent, what can be omitted? While some scholars aim to preserve as much source information as possible to enhance the readability of their encodings, others prioritize solutions that ensure the immediate interoperability of the files. For early music, for example, it is common practice to omit *musica ficta* accidentals from visualizations in order to maximize the logical readability of encoded files, particularly when they are intended for analytical purposes.

Staves, measures (where present), pitches, rhythmic indications, and dynamics are certainly necessary to properly understand and appreciate the work on a semiotic as well as aesthetic level. MEI format provides ready access to this information and immediately conveys the main characteristics of the piece, complementing the metadata. However, it is important to keep in mind – as this guide has repeatedly emphasized – that a digital edition should not merely be a digitized version of a traditional edition : its strength lies in the semantic encoding of previously inaccessible information. Consequently, SVG renderings should not be regarded as absolute witnesses to the source (which will be linked and consultable directly) but rather as a computational interpretation that facilitates work with the musical data.

Software such as Sibelius and MuseScore nevertheless allow the addition of text, symbols, and objects associated with specific musical conventions (e.g. *ficta*, *hauptstimme*, *nebenstimme*) which can carry semantic value within MEI files, either natively or through manual modification of the code. The Verovio viewer guidelines for preparing files further emphasize the importance of maintaining simplicity in file preparation and ensuring that metadata are linked to well-established reference systems : “When loading MEI data into Verovio and outputting MEI,

elements that are not supported by Verovio will be ignored. This means that they are not loaded into memory and will not be preserved in the MEI output.”¹

It is also possible to include the incipits of works within .mei files ; these are important for establishing a faithful connection between the encoding and the source by specifying the keys and integer valor, thereby reflecting the editor’s critical judgment (fig. 17). The incipit is declared in the file header and treated as metadata. In the online visualization, the main file and the incipit are displayed separately.

3.2. Creating a Presentation Model

In the Western tradition, musical works are conceptually regarded as fixed under an idealized notion of completeness. Within the FRBR framework discussed above, the work refers to the intellectual creation itself, viewed at its most general and conceptual level. Each edition, however, constitutes a distinct manifestation of that work, a concept that can be extended to individual copies annotated by performers, composers, etc. (referred to as items in FRBR). Consequently, the number of incarnations of the work is virtually proportional to its editions, transcriptions, arrangements, and even individual performances. All of these experiences together contribute to the richness with which we perceive the work, as reflected in the long trajectory of critical editions that reveals the aesthetic and historiographical reflections that have interested musicologists.

It is therefore reasonable to ask whether digital critical editions should strive to be exhaustive – by encoding variants directly within the work – or be deliberately

fig. 17: *Serf j'ai esté non point en vain*, Jean Servin ; Verovio visualization of the work and its incipit.

scientifically selective. Above all, it seems essential to emphasize that the scholarly approach to digital critical editions must differ from that to printed critical editions, particularly the study of genetic relationships between sources through both quantitative and qualitative analysis of variants.

¹ L. Pugin, *Reference Book For Verovio* version 5.1, 15 April 2025, 10.5448/7em6-my23, p. 62.

3.2.1. Annotation Spaces and Multimodality

Annotation spaces are an essential feature for users. Their accessibility must be carefully designed because they are key areas of critical work. In the case of MEI, it is advisable to follow guidelines closely in order to ensure clearly readable encoding,¹ especially important when annotations multiply. A specific development phase must then be undertaken to adapt the viewer interface to editorial needs. It should be noted, however, that setting up such a space on a dynamic website remains a challenging task because it requires substantial technical expertise. Implementing an annotation space therefore depends on considerable human and scholarly resources, ideally supported by a dedicated team assembled in advance, and, if possible, external funding.

A particularly clear example that combines the display of MEI files and a critical apparatus can be found in the digital Marenzio edition (fig. 18). Here, annotation is carried out during the editorial process and reflects the *collatio* as well as any potential editorial choices:

In the more complex context of collaborative annotation projects such as *Gesualdo Online*, the Ricercar+Data+Lab incorporates a score viewer that allows users to display either the MEI code or the critical apparatus, with variants and annotations, alongside the score (fig. 19). Registered users can add annotations that refer to one or more notes; these annotations can be categorized by type (“Duration”, “Emendation”, “Pitch”, etc.), and accompanied by textual content. The contributor responsible for each annotation is identified. A permissions system determines whether users are allowed to annotate the original MEI file directly

or whether their annotations must be placed in a duplicate file pending validation by an administrator. Once validated, annotations can then be integrated into the original file.

fig. 18: *Se bramate ch'io mora*, Luca Marenzio, export in .mei format published on the project website via the Verovio viewer.

1. Se bramate ch'io mora

Measures	Sources – Voices	Variants
1	AnGa-1593 Sc-heir-1603 AnGa-1605	all voices mensuration sign C-cut instead of C
12	Vi-1587 – C	f4 originally g4, then corrected in all copies. In US-BEM there is no correction to f4, but the body of the note is erased.
24	AnGa-1605 – B	e2 instead of d2

¹ See 10. Critical Apparatus, <https://music-encoding.org/guidelines/v3/content/critapp.html> as well as the tag <annot> for annotation in <https://music-encoding.org/guidelines/v3/elements/annot.html>

fig. 19: score viewer on the Ricercar+Data+Lab website.

The panel on the right displays the critical apparatus, including variants and annotations contributed by registered users. Three versions of this apparatus can be viewed: the original edition, the version in source A, or the version in source B. Notes shown in red on the score indicate elements that have variants and/or annotations, while elements in blue correspond to those selected by the user. If annotations pertain to these elements, a popup window appears displaying the annotation content (fig. 20).

In general and to ensure that the document is easily readable, it is recommended to select a minimal yet meaningful set of criteria for annotations that make a particular copy relevant, so that the significance of the source remains perceptible. The critical apparatus can also include audio files, such as MIDI files or live or studio recordings, making it easier for non-musicological communities to participate. The inclusion of audio in digital critical editions is indeed a key

fig. 20: annotation submission form (the notes shown in blue in the background are those selected by the user for the annotation).

concern. At present, only a very small number of projects succeed in synchronizing audio files with encoded files.¹

3.2.2. Musical Analysis and Postprocessing Encoded Files

MEI encoding offers semantic advantages that facilitate establishing links between data, making it a particularly promising field for research in musical analysis. Numerous tools have been developed to perform batch operations across large numbers of MEI files, most often using the Python programming language. Owing to its structured organization, MEI lends itself well to exploring and studying motifs within large *corpora*. Music21 is one of the most advanced tools for recognizing musical motifs within a corpus, while also enabling complex analytical tasks, such as identifying the instability of the rhythmic profile of a piece or preparing

¹ Some pieces in the Marenzio edition synchronize the MEI encoding with audio files.

thematic catalogues within a specific corpus by grouping pieces according to key, meter, etc.¹

CRIM Intervals, which builds on Music21, provides sophisticated identification of melodic, harmonic, and contrapuntal motifs characteristic of Renaissance polyphony. It was developed within the project *Citations: The Renaissance Imitation Mass*²:

fig. 21: An example of pitch visualization for a work, generated using Music21.³

As noted above, Humdrum is well suited to analysis due to its system of commands, which can be combined with one another. It is not limited to the tonal analysis of music : it can also detect patterns by systematically examining intervals. In addition, it enables similarity measures (correlation, edit distance), and performs editing operations using settheoretic formalism,⁴ which makes it particularly well suited to more complex *corpora*.

Regarding postprocessing, Richard Freedman⁵ has also developed several tools (*mei_tools*⁶) that enable the simultaneous updating of metadata across a large number of MEI files from a single document, as well as the correction of minor engraving errors introduced by software idiosyncrasies. Another notable tool is *Mermeid*,⁷ which supports the management, (pre)visualization, and manipulation of metadata embedded in files. These tools can be particularly valuable when working with dense *corpora* or when mass modifications are required.

3.3. Relationships with Sources

The digital lens allows us to rethink the critical edition by providing direct access to sources via the IIIF protocol. This is a standardized methodology for sharing, annotating, and preserving images, which appears particularly well suited to the digitization of musical sources. Indeed:

1 For more information, see <https://www.music21.org/music21docs/about/what.html>

2 See <https://crimproject.org/>

3 For the complete example, see the following link : https://www.music21.org/music21docs/usersGuide/usersGuide_15_key.html

4 A concrete example of analysis can be consulted via this link : http://recherche.ircam.fr/equipes/repmus/Analyse/Humdrum/humdrum_exemple.html

5 <https://www.haverford.edu/users/rfreedma>

6 For more information, see https://github.com/RichardFreedman/mei_tools/blob/main/README.md

7 For more information, see <https://mermeid.edirom.de/manual/basics.html>

IIIF allows for the efficient comparison of musical scores and notations across various collections, significantly easing the analysis of compositional similarities, stylistic evolutions, and regional variations. It also empowers musicologists to access, study, and share high-quality images of medieval music manuscripts that might otherwise be confined to their physical locations.¹

Between the digital rewriting of a source and the digitization of the original manuscript, it is now possible to exploit large datasets and to refine analytical procedures in support of editorial decisions that a traditional edition could not accommodate. In the context of early music – from the study of the *Ars antiqua* through the XVI^e century – numerous issues inherent to musical notation arise, such as the faithful transcription of ligatures in notation software, which often struggles to capture the precise subtleties of handwritten calligraphy. The availability of a digitized source therefore helps to overcome these difficulties by combining graphical fidelity with the interoperability of encoding. One relevant approach could involve designing synoptic editions, creating direct visual links between manuscripts and recordings, thereby facilitating the interpretation of tripla and mensural proportions.

It is essential to address the question of access to sources for users of digital editions to enable a better understanding of historical practices, particularly regarding prosody and musical arrangements. Indeed, while some variants may be considered negligible, others are crucial for interpretation. Access to sources

is generally possible through two main avenues : a link to a resource hosted by an institution that has previously worked on or directly digitized the source, or through an IIIF viewer integrated directly into the digital edition. It is nevertheless important to consider the legal implications of such decisions, taking into account the location and institutional ownership of the sources, as well as, where applicable, pre-existing digitizations, which must be properly referenced.

The *Polish Music Heritage* project offers an ideal model : connections between digital scores and digitized sources are explored using IIIF. It is thus possible to zoom in on the manuscript maintaining excellent image quality, and easily access all the information related to the document's dimensions and format, accompanied by a color scale to verify hues (**fig. 22**). The interface is user friendly and compatible with diverse formats (PDF, MEI, Humdrum, etc.).

1 X. Fresquet (December 4, 2022). IIIF and the Connectivity of Medieval Mediterranean Music Collections. *MnemoMed*. Retrieved February 6, 2025 from <https://doi.org/10.58079/vwx2>

fig. 22: *sza na Cztery głosy* by Wincenty Studziński and Piotr — digitization of the score¹ and visualization of the transcription in MEL.²

Archives and Library of Cracow Cathedral Chapter

Composer/Author
Studziński, Wincenty

Title on source
[title page, f. 1:] Msza na | Cztery głosy przez | Wincentego Studzińskiego i Piotra (bracia)

Standardized title
Msza

Date
[c. 1850]

Voice/Instrument
S; A; T; B

Format, extent
Parts; 19 f.

Dimensions
32 cm x 25 cm

Related person (Function)
Studziński, Piotr (Co-composer);

Subject heading

3.4. Data Lifecycle, Management, Accessibility, and Reuse

The management of the data lifecycle is a central component of institutional data management policies. It aims to oversee all stages – from creation to archiving or destruction – while ensuring data quality, security, and accessibility. From the moment of their creation, data must be

Polish Digital Scores

Wincenty Studziński
1815-1854
IMSLP RISM VIAF Wikidata

Wawel Cathedral, Cracow
PL-Kk: Kk.1.476

Msza
Kirie

Soprano
Kirie
Ky - ri - e - le - - - i - son

Kyrie
Alto
Ky - ri - e - lej - son Ky - ri - e e - lej - son

Tenore
Ky - ri - e - lej - son e - lej - son Ky - ri - e e - lej - son

Basfo
Ky - ri - e e - lej - son e - lej - son Ky - ri - e e - lej - son

Masza na 4ry Glosy
Ki - ri - e e lej - son e - lei - - - son - ri - e - e - lej - son -

documented and stored according to institutional and legal standards to guarantee their integrity and potential for reuse. During their use, governance mechanisms should enable control over their usage and sharing in compliance with regulatory and legal frameworks, particularly concerning the protection of sensitive data. [...]³

1 This source can be consulted via this link : <https://polish.musicsources.pl/en/lokalizacje/galeria/rekopisy/6083-msza/3>

2 The encoding can be consulted via this link : <https://polish.musicsources.pl/en/lokalizacje/11-archives-and-library-of-cracow-cathedral-chapter>

3 Our translation of <https://data.unige.ch/cycle-de-vie/etapes-du-cycle-de-vie>

3.4.1. Digital Edition or Database

Given the power and comprehensiveness of the tools now available, the boundary between a digital edition equipped with a critical apparatus and a database must be examined. Indeed, the introduction of an excessive number of metadata fields and crossreferences can sometimes shift the musical paradigm toward a knowledge organization system with a historiographical focus, thereby diluting the primary information. It is therefore important to ensure that a project's feasibility is not compromised by overly ambitious goals.

From the earliest stages of an editorial project, it is necessary to question which fields and crossreferences are absolutely necessary to initiate the creation of an Open Access project. Should priority be given to the strictly musical and analytical study of a composer's works, or rather to their historiography, the locations of their performances, and their reception history? While the former clearly falls within the scope of a critical music edition, the latter would benefit far more from a database architecture, whether relational or semantic.

Dezède stands out among databases that offer considerable richness, advanced functionality, and a the opportunity for collaboration : this opensource web application is specifically designed to archive performances and put them in chronological order. Maintained by an active community, it “fosters the development of research on the circulation of works and performers, by providing researchers and the public with a wealth of historical data.”¹

fig. 22: Chordal graph representation of the most performed composers at Royaumont Abbey between 1936 and 1977² (shown alongside).

1 <https://dezede.org/presentation>

2 The graph is interactive and allows users to visualize which composers were most frequently performed together : <https://dezede.org/dossiers/concerts-abbaye-de-royaumont/stats>

These issues particularly affect digital editions in MEI format. Given the format's powerful interoperability, it can be tempting to overload files with meta-data and references that exceed the project's original objectives and complicate the editorial process. It is therefore important to remain attentive to these issues so that the edition remains, above all, an effective tool for its users and can be easily updated, a task that is made easier when the project's technical architecture is planned from the outset.

3.4.2. Data Sustainability and Visibility

Although many secure local alternatives exist, data storage and hosting on servers remains costly. Virtual machines¹ can be provided by universities or large research infrastructures (notably the IR* HumaNum for the Humanities and Social Sciences). Storing data on national servers offers numerous advantages, particularly for publicly funded and Open Access projects, but also presents disadvantages in more complex geopolitical situations.

The French government has recently proposed a list of secure repositories for the humanities and social sciences,² including Nakala, which is used for projects associated with IR* HumaNum. It is a "data repository that aims to preserve and disseminate data produced by French research projects in the Humanities and Social Sciences, in compliance with the FAIR principles" and "is primarily intended for research projects carried out by institutions affiliated with the French

Ministry of Higher Education and Research."³ In a similar spirit – also hosted by HumaNum but focused specifically on musical content – NEUMA can be cited as "a digital library that gives on-line access to rare and often hardly accessible corpora. [...]"⁴

The final stage of an edition thus involves making a well-considered and appropriate choice for stable and highquality hosting of data, combined with a userfriendly consultation interface.

1 A virtual machine is a digital version of a physical computer, stored on and running from a physical machine. It can host an operating system and, consequently, databases, as well as perform computations and other tasks.

2 <https://recherche.data.gouv.fr/fr/entrepots>

3 <https://www.nakala.fr/about>

4 <https://neuma.huma-num.fr/>

4.1. Checklist for Digital Editions; What are the Essential Steps ?

Having outlined the main issues associated with editing music using digital tools, readers of this guide should now be prepared to begin a first edition of a short work. The checklist below provides a foundation for beginning the editorial process, ensuring that all the main steps are observed :

- ▀ Is my corpus clearly defined ?
- ▀ Do I need to reconstruct the work, or is it complete ?
- ▀ Have I decided to produce a diplomatic edition or a critical edition ?
- ▀ If I have chosen to prepare a critical edition, do I have access to all existing editions ?
- ▀ If I digitized the sources myself, did I respect IIIF protocol ?
- ▀ Have I clearly defined the intended audience for my edition? Students, the musical community, and/or musicologists ?
- ▀ Does my project adhere to the budget and schedule allocated to it ?
- ▀ Have I considered the expected dissemination model– Open Access or subscription-based format ?
- ▀ Have I identified the encoding software¹ I will use as well as the formats I wish to employ for export² ?

Once my file has been exported, I must ensure that metadata are specified precisely:

- ▀ Have I included all essential metadata, ensured interoperability, and linked the work to its RISM ID ?
- ▀ Have I cited my sources ?

- ▀ Have I acknowledged all contributors to the edition ?
- ▀ Assigned a license (Creative Commons, etc.) to my work ?

Once the file metadata are complete, the next step is visualization:

- ▀ Am I satisfied with the quality of the rendering in a viewer ?
- ▀ Have I confirmed that the file has been validated in MEIfriend ?
- ▀ Am I satisfied with the quality of my encoding for the purpose of analysis?
- ▀ Have I defined a clear strategy for annotating variants?
- ▀ Is the user interface sufficiently clear ?
- ▀ Have I identified a trusted repository for depositing my data ?
- ▀ Have I ensured that my edition is correctly indexed and referenced ?

1 In early 2025, in light of indications that the development of Sibelius may no longer be maintained, we recommend using MuseScore, which provides numerous advantages through its Open-Source design and its easy compatibility with the MEI format.

2 Given its interoperability, flexibility, and easy export from MuseScore, we recommend using MEI format, whose visualization is fully supported by Verovio.